

Art's Uncomfortable Answer: Rethinking Tourism circularity through Waste

Abstract

This chapter explores the paradoxes of sustainability and circularity in tourism through the conceptual and material lens of waste. Drawing on the Wasteocene framework (Armiero, 2021), it critically examines how both material and symbolic waste – generated by overtourism and the commodification of local cultures – reflect structural inequalities embedded in contemporary capitalism. Two contrasting case studies in the Veneto region, Venice and the Dolomites, serve as experimental contexts for Cultural Living Labs (CLLs) based on art-led, participatory methodologies. Within these labs, waste cooking oil (WCO) became a central metaphor and material for rethinking circular economy narratives and activating situated, collective forms of knowledge. Through creative practices such as cooking, drawing, and storytelling, local participants reimagined waste as a cultural, affective, and epistemological resource rather than as residue. The artistic process revealed how communities can “care for waste” by transforming discarded materials and memories into critical and imaginative tools for resistance, belonging, and sustainability. The chapter proposes an alternative model of circularity – one grounded in care, relationality, and cultural re-signification rather than in techno-managerial efficiency.

Keywords: sustainable tourism, circular economy, Wasteocene, art-based research, community resilience, symbolic waste, cultural heritage, participatory methodology, care, Venice and Dolomites

Introduction

Tourism is one of the sectors most subject to tensions and contradictions. On the one hand, there are opportunities for economic growth, strategies to promote environmental sustainability and recognition of unique local cultures; on the other hand, there are negative impacts on both socio-cultural and environmental levels. One of the main problems associated with tourism is the huge amount of material waste (single-use plastic, food packaging, and organic waste from restaurants and accommodation), considered real “social costs” (Pizam, 1978). Added to this is the symbolic and cultural waste generated from commercialising territories, often for tourism purposes. This often contributes to damaging local cultures and silencing community voices in favour of narratives and stereotypes that serve the consumption and commodification of memories and landscapes (Bender et al., 2013; Rickly, 2022).

The Veneto region is a suitable context for observing and comparing these dynamics, where common challenges emerge despite the differences between areas in the region. The project *Sustainable Business Models for Tourism with a Culture-Based Approach*, supported by funding awarded to young researchers from Ca' Foscari University of Venice within the PNRR iNEST (Interconnected Nord-Est Innovation Ecosystem) was developed by an interdisciplinary team of researchers from fields including management, linguistics, chemistry, fine arts, anthropology, among others. The project analysed two case studies, chosen for their complicated and contradictory relationship with tourism. The first was Venice, the heritage city par excellence, which still attracts millions of tourists every year, located in a fragile socio-

ecological environment characterised by mass tourism, gentrification and declining residential population. The second case study dealt with the Dolomites of Belluno, with particular attention paid to Colle Santa Lucia and Arabba, small Ladin communities strongly linked to natural heritage, affected by depopulation and strongly dependent on a tourist monoculture. The team decided to draw inspiration from the concept of the Wasteocene (Armiero, 2021; Armiero and De Angelis, 2017) and use it as a basic theoretical framework to problematise the category of “waste”, central to their analysis. Unlike other concepts such as the Anthropocene (Hecht, 2018), which tends to homogenise ecological responsibility by attributing the impact on the planet to the generic *Anthropos*, and its alternatives, which seek to problematise the concept - such as the Capitalocene (Davis et al., 2019), the Plantationocene (Paredes, 2021; Manjapra, 2018), or the Chthulucene (Haraway, 2015), the Wasteocene highlights the systemic production and disposal of waste as characteristic features of contemporary socio-ecological relations. This theoretical perspective enabled the team to reflect on the structural inequalities and practices of marginalisation that generate both material and symbolic waste, and to demonstrate how the concept of waste, both as tangible matter and as a system of wasteful relations, is constitutive of modern capitalism. Following Armiero (2021) and Armiero and De Angelis (2017), the concept enabled the research group to interpret material and cultural refuse as indicators of the power structures that shape territories, economies, and imaginaries, and to show how people and communities themselves can become waste by being marginalised through profit-driven models of development.

The researchers posed a central question: How can waste serve as a theoretical and methodological framework to imagine a new understanding of the cultural and environmental impacts of tourism, and to support truly sustainable, circular alternative models? The category of waste has proven to be a useful tool for illustrating how practices, knowledge, and landscapes are devalued or transformed into stereotyped and commodified versions of local culture (Jones and Wynn, 2018; Power et al., 2024).

Cultural Living Labs (CLLs) were developed within the project, led primarily by an artist. These labs served as spaces for participatory experimentation where local communities, researchers, and the leading artist collaborated to co-create knowledge, reactivate narratives, and identify tourism-related issues. The CLLs adopted an art-based methodological approach, in which artistic practices were conceived not only as means of expression but also as tools for investigating and experimenting with nonlinear, affective, and performative forms of knowledge. This approach enabled participants to engage critically, allowing them to articulate alternative narratives and imaginaries about how sustainable tourism practices are conceived. Unlike the quantitative and qualitative methodologies typical of the social sciences, artistic research thus allowed us to focus on both ineffability and the processes of knowledge construction (Boyd and Barry, 2024). Within the workshops, the concept of waste was used as a theoretical framework to analyse and interpret the processes of socio-material and symbolic marginalisation of social groups and local communities marked by the advent of monocultural tourism, as well as to reactivate memories, values, and practices.

The reflection started from a tangible object and issue: the disposal and necessary reuse of a specific type of waste - used cooking oil - as produced by the catering industry. On the one hand, it was considered as a concrete environmental problem as it difficult to collect and dispose of, especially in sensitive areas such as Venice and the Alpine regions. On the other hand, it represents a potential resource that can be recycled as part of circular production models (for a detailed description of the process please refer to Baldan, 2025, Chapter XXX).

This dual nature has highlighted that both tangible and intangible aspects of local culture are at risk of being marginalised by unsustainable tourism models, while also allowing the research team and interlocutors to imagine alternative links between tourism, community, and the environment. It is precisely because of the link between waste oil and gastronomy that the artist and the other researchers decided to work in CLLs primarily in this sector - of key importance to the tourism industry – involving restaurant businesses and kitchen staff. During the CLLs, the research group adopted a methodological approach that encouraged the spontaneous emergence of informants' reflections through non-linear and 'rhizomatic' thought processes (Deleuze and Guattari, 1980). These processes enabled the combination of material, symbolic, and conceptual elements across multiple connections, generating new possibilities for interpretation. In this context, the creative transformation of used oils emerged as both a theoretical and methodological tool, capable of fostering critical reflection on business models related to sustainable tourism.

Paradox in tourism

Tourism has historically been promoted as a sustainable alternative to other industries, particularly heavy manufacturing and petrochemical plants. In the 1950s and 1960s, it was envisioned as a way to provide economic diversification and foster the cultural identity of territories, without the destructive consequences associated with industrial development (Favero and Moretti, 2017). This early framing positioned tourism as a sector capable of ensuring economic growth for places and marginal regions (as part of a rhetoric of regeneration), and it quickly became central to discourses on local development and sustainability. Tourism is widely recognised as an important driver of economic growth, providing employment and opportunities for host communities (UNWTO, 2017). Its role in supporting regional economies was especially emphasised in peripheral or remote areas, where it is often perceived as vital for development (Hall, 2008). From this perspective, tourism has been presented not only as a source of income but also as a catalyst for positive change, capable of alleviating poverty and contributing to the long-term viability of natural and human resources (Bramwell and Lane, 1993). However, from as early as the 1980s, scholars had started to address issues relating to tourism, raising concerns about the capacity of places to sustain it (O'Reilly, 1986).

In response to these concerns, the concept of "sustainable tourism" gained traction as an alternative to the main tourism industry. Bramwell and Lane (1993: 2) were the first to define sustainable tourism as:

"[...] a positive approach intended to reduce the tensions and friction created by the complex interactions between the tourism industry, visitors, the environment and the communities which are host to holidaymakers. It is an approach which involves working for the long-term viability and quality of

both natural and human resources. It is not anti-growth, but it acknowledges that there are limits to growth.”

Despite its aura of “sustainability”, this narrative tends to obscure the contradictions and structural limitations of tourism as a vehicle for sustainable development (Boluk et al., 2019), as well as the inequitable distribution of resources and wealth accumulation among a small elite (Buscher and Fletcher, 2017). Despite its promises, the sector has been slow to reinvent its business models in ways that genuinely address socio-environmental and cultural dilemmas (Power et al., 2024). While it continues to promise sustainability, tourism remains heavily dependent on fossil fuels, energy-intensive infrastructure, and globalised supply chains (Hollenhorst, Houge-Mackenzie, and Ostergren, 2014). Rather than overcoming industrial logics, it reproduces the linear “take-make-waste” model of production and consumption (Singer, 2017). Consequently, the tourism industry continues to contribute significantly to environmental degradation through practices such as inadequate waste management, biodiversity loss, and increased carbon emissions. Tourism monoculture, in addition to generating material waste due to poor waste management, also produces symbolic and cultural waste resulting from the commercialisation of experiences and gentrification processes that devalue the intrinsic meaning of destinations, transforming them into commodities for visitors. As a result, landscapes are stereotyped and local voices silenced (Sailesh, 2024), leading to their marginalisation in decision-making processes (Freire-Medeiros, 2013). These dynamics entail significant environmental and social costs for communities (Bender et al., 2013; Jones and Wynn, 2018), exacerbate existing inequalities, perpetuate stereotypical representations, and distance the tourist experience from the authenticity of local cultures and environments (Bender et al., 2013; Rickly, 2022), thus compromising the very promise of sustainability. These processes can be traced back to what Armiero calls wasted relationships (Armiero, 2021), referring to the tendency to devalue the identities of destinations and reproduce stereotypes that distance tourists from the authenticity of local cultures (Rickly, 2022).

Hollinshead (1992) described the tourist encounter as an “objectifying gaze”, echoing concerns about inequality (Turner and Ash, 1975), power (Bianchi, 2009), and the lack of morality in tourism consumption and production (Weeden and Boluk, 2014). In light of these contradictions, scholars have increasingly focused on the ephemeral nature of sustainability goals (Higgins-Desbiolles, 2010; Moscardo and Hughes, 2018) and have sought to deconstruct the dominant narratives of sustainable tourism by focusing on power relations (Boluk et al., 2019), postcolonial dynamics (Hall and Tucker, 2004), gender inequality (Ferguson and Alarcón, 2015), and environmental justice (Higgins-Desbiolles and Powys Whyte, 2014) to examine tourism systems from different perspectives, such as marginalised communities and underrepresented populations (Boluk et al., 2019). Critical tourism research has also highlighted the need to rethink governance models and promote greater inclusion of marginalised or underrepresented social groups. These new perspectives aim to incorporate

pluralistic worldviews into decision-making processes and recognise the active role of humans and non-humans in ecosystems (Boluk et al., 2019). However, the sector still lacks a radical restructuring of its business models capable of addressing the deepest socio-ecological and cultural dilemmas.

The paradox of the sustainable business model in the tourism industry

The challenges posed by tourism thus highlight an institutional complexity (Greenwood et al., 2011) that cannot be solved by maintaining current business models. In response to these critical issues, the dominant narrative in sustainability management discourses has increasingly emphasised the circular economy paradigm, which has become central to business model innovation, and in particular to the ideal of transforming waste into a resource (Fedele and Formisano, 2023; Moalem et al., 2022). This view, first theorised in the work of Havlicek et al. (1969) to reflect the idea that waste is a resource and not a problem, became increasingly important in waste management in the 1990s (e.g. Stessel 1996; Tammemagi 1999), and has subsequently been institutionalised through legal frameworks such as Directive 2008/98/EC. The circular economy prescribes a hierarchy of avoidance, reuse, recycling, and finally disposal. This utilitarian perspective has become widely accepted, including the use of waste as an input for green energy production (Veolia, 2023). The approach reflects what Hultman et al. (2021) describe as a fundamental assertion of human efficiency: The optimistic belief that even discarded, broken, or devaluated materials can be reused as valuable resources through innovation. However, as Corvellec (2025) convincingly argues, such models are based on what the philosopher François Jullien (2004) calls heroic efficiency, a Western notion based on goal-orientation, planning, and the pursuit of an ideal future. From this perspective, circular business models are not only a practical response to environmental degradation. They also embody a management ideology that celebrates the ability to turn failure into opportunity and neutralise the negativity of waste. Narratives of closed material loops and zero waste ambitions are based on valorising waste itself as the limit of entrepreneurial ingenuity. This vision risks obscuring the deeper structural causes of overproduction, consumption, and environmental injustice (Gregson and Crang, 2015). Moreover, the circular economy promotes an ecomodernism concept in which society and nature are formally integrated, while materials are treated as separable and controllable flows (Levidow and Raman, 2020). We can, therefore, also recognise an important paradox in the circular economy: instead of questioning the logic of accumulation, the circular economy often reproduces it more subtly by introducing new waste into the cycle and ignoring the costs of transformation. Waste is re-commodified and integrated into systems that prioritise efficiency and value creation. The re-commodification of waste into a cycle can even lead to rebound effects that increase overall material production (Greer et al., 2021), contradicting the very goal they claim to achieve. Indeed, the pursuit of zero waste remains a symbolic horizon rather than a viable transition strategy (Kirchherr et al., 2023). This tendency to ascribe value to waste in narratives about the circular economy reflects what Mary Douglas (1966) describes as the social construction of *dirt*, which is understood as *out of place* and as such represents a danger that needs to be controlled. According to Douglas, what appears as dirt is the product of a society's categories and symbolic boundaries. This 'classifying' dimension is related to what Corvellec (2025) observed: the heroic notion of circular efficiency tends to place the unintended consequences of its own effectiveness outside its epistemological boundaries, relegating everything that exceeds this

framework to the dimension of "waste". In this way, not only are alternative forms of knowledge and practices excluded, but also the geopolitical asymmetries and socio-material inequalities inherent in waste management. In this context, the symbolic and material marginalisation caused by circular economy narratives finds a parallel in the dynamics of tourism: The same classificatory logic that define what is valuable and what is "waste" also operate in decision-making processes, and exclude local knowledge and diverse visions. Given this structural lack of empowerment of local communities, critical tourism research has highlighted the need to rethink governance models and promote greater inclusion of marginalised or underrepresented social groups. These new considerations aim to promote greater openness to plural worldviews in decision-making processes while recognising the active roles of humans and non-humans in ecosystems (Boluk et al., 2019). Nevertheless, the sector lacks a radical restructuring of its business models that could address these profound socio-ecological and cultural dilemmas.

Contexts of research, methodology, and findings

Contexts of research

The geographical areas selected for this project - Venice and the Dolomites (particularly Colle Santa Lucia and Arabba) - were chosen because of their complex and conflictual relationship with tourism. In Venice, the effects of mass tourism are closely linked to depopulation processes which accelerated during the second half of the 20th century (Favero and Moretti, 2017). Both depopulation and the emergence of a tourism monoculture can be traced to the unforeseen consequences of the "Greater Venice" intervention project, which envisaged the industrial and residential development of Mestre and Marghera as playing a part in promoting the cultural and tourist transformation of Venice and its Lido. The combination of the exodus, the socio-political changes of the time, and the rapid growth of mass tourism prevented the continuation of many social practices that historically and culturally characterised the daily use of urban spaces (e.g. local markets and craft workshops as places of exchange and interaction, field festivals and religious celebrations experienced as communal moments, forms of neighbourly conviviality in the small squares and streets, and children playing in public spaces). The lack of a critical mass of inhabitants, combined with the economic dominance of tourism today, undermines the authenticity of the place (Montanari, 2011) and makes the development of a truly creative territory almost impossible (Scott, 2006), as any initiative is quickly absorbed in the process of touristification. At the same time, the Dolomites, which include the areas of Colle Santa Lucia and Arabba, have experienced particularly critical forms of mass tourism in the last half-century (e.g. Tre Cime di Lavaredo), involving a significant impact on the environment and infrastructures (Collavo, 2025). In the specific area of the Agordina Valley (which includes Colle Santa Lucia and Arabba), demographic analysis carried out between 2001 and 2024 has documented a loss of 1,300 inhabitants, from about 12,545 in 2001 to about 11,200 in 2023, which corresponds to an average decrease of about 6-7 inhabitants per month. In particular, the population of Colle Santa Lucia decreased from 404 inhabitants in 2001 to about 346 in 2024, confirming a constant trend of depopulation (Santin, 2022; ISTAT data). There are also considerable socio-economic inequalities in the Dolomites. Some established tourist resorts enjoy a high level of economic development and prosperity,

fuelled by world-class mass tourism. In contrast, small and remote settlements where tourism is still in its infancy suffer from social, demographic, and economic marginalisation, while traditional primary activities (forestry, agriculture, livestock) are in decline (Murphy, 1985).

Methodology

In social science research, the epistemological assumptions that determine the validity of an investigation are traditionally situated within two main paradigms: Qualitative and quantitative. The former favours an in-depth, often intimate exploration of phenomena through approaches based on textual or verbal narratives, while the latter relies on systematic procedures using large-scale surveys or population questionnaires (Goopy and Kassan, 2019). In this study, the research team instead adopted an arts-based approach (Leavy, 2018) to explore innovative ways of engaging participants and analysing knowledge construction processes. Specifically, researchers observed that knowledge development doesn't only follow a rational, linear, and hierarchical approach, but also follows a rhizomatic one (Deleuze and Guattari, 1980) which values the spontaneous emergence of connections and insights. Within this framework, artist Elena Mazzi participated as an integral part of the project. Her works, rooted in the examination of specific territories, reinterpret the cultural and natural heritage of places by intertwining stories, facts, and memories passed down by local communities to suggest possible solutions to the conflict between humanity, nature, and culture. Her method, in close dialogue with anthropological approaches and methodologies, favours a holistic perspective aimed at healing social fractures and tensions. This approach, based on close observation and understanding the needs of local groups, was implemented through the experimental use of CLLs in the two tourist locations of Venice and the Dolomites in the Veneto region. The arts-based methodology was divided into three interconnected phases, Initiation, Work and Result, and Debriefing, each designed to centralise marginalised voices, ascribe value to cultural practices, and reconfigure waste as a resource, both materially and symbolically.

In this project, in line with several scholars who have identified culture as a lever for change (Lockwood and Soublière, 2022; Lounsbury et al., 2001, 2019), culture was understood as an artistic process in dialogue with the principles of the circular economy within the context of CLLs. Here, artistic practices not only used recycled or reused materials, but also served as critical and creative theoretical tools to rethink cycles of production, consumption, and waste, both materially and symbolically.

The research was structured as follows:

Setup Phase – Narrative Collection

The research began by collecting “waste stories” - narratives about everyday practices of waste management and reuse, from community stakeholders, including restaurateurs, food industry workers, and associations. Narratives were collected through semi-structured interviews and situated practices, such as cooking together, to generate embodied and relational forms of knowledge (Halbwachs, 2020). The artist, together with researchers, interviewed operators from the food and hospitality sector during November and December 2024 and March 2025. A total of 15 interviews were conducted.

Creative Living Labs

The CLLs were designed as spaces of experimentation where communities, the artist, and researchers could reframe and discuss the contradictions of tourism monocultures and hospitality waste. In Venice, two workshops of 3 hours each were held. In the Dolomites, one longer workshop of 4 hours took place, conducted in part in a restaurant kitchen. Each session included two components:

1. Knowledge-Sharing – researchers presented interdisciplinary insights on waste materials, particularly waste cooking oil (WCO), highlighting both its technical reuse potential (e.g. biodiesel, plastics, cement; Cárdenas et al., 2021; Foo et al., 2022) and its metaphorical role as residual waste from tourism-driven consumption.
2. Memory Bridge and Collective Imagination – participants connected personal food-related memories with contemporary socio-environmental challenges, thereby constructing a “*memory bridge*” between past and present. Participants were invited to bring personal items and receipts connected to food memories, which served as prompts for storytelling and as symbolic artefacts linking material culture to lived experience. This approach reflects the principles of arts-based research (Leavy, 2018), whereby creative processes support data collection while mitigating extractivist tendencies. To ensure reciprocity, all participants received reimbursement fees, to recognise their contributions and to avoid reproducing asymmetrical relationships as part of the research. Through storytelling, drawings, and collaborative reflection, participants collectively re-imagined alternative futures.

The CLLs functioned as situated, participatory environments that fostered the development of alternative imaginaries, bottom-up futures, and forms of socio-ecological resilience co-created with local communities. The theoretical perspective of waste enabled a critical rethinking of the category of discarded material and immaterial things, and highlighted the processes through which dominant systems ascribe value while creating marginalisation. Discussions with participants revealed emic interpretations of the mechanisms that maintain these asymmetries, and showed how waste can become a space for knowledge, resistance, creativity, and symbolic renegotiation. In this process of co-constructing knowledge, waste has been considered as an important epistemological and cognitive tool (Bourriaud, 1998), capable of giving voice to marginalised and invisible interpretations, often absent from dominant narratives, and translated into the artist's drawings. As Pussetti (2019) points out, the creative and artistic process represents an increasingly significant research tool that can open up spaces for reflection and co-creation that are difficult to achieve through prescriptive or hierarchical methods. From a methodological perspective, the drawings made during or after the CLLs not only preserved the memory of specific situations but also expanded the possibilities for analysis and interpretation. In line with Kashanipour (2021), they represented a stepwise approach to the understanding and production of knowledge, involving both the unlearning of consolidated categories and the learning of new, potentially related categories.

Participant selections

In the two locations analysed, (Venice and the municipalities in the Dolomites), particular attention was paid to restaurateurs, key actors in local tourism.

Characteristics of participants varied according to age, culinary offer, type of venue, and target audience. In the Venetian case study, independent individuals without a fixed workplace, with a more nomadic and performative approach were also involved, as were associations and cooking schools. In the Dolomites, individuals, associations, and personalities specifically linked to the Ladin community were also involved.

While restaurateurs are often identified as producers of food waste (material waste), in this project they were also recognised as actors involved in the dynamics of symbolic and immaterial waste, which are usually marginalised in the discourse around tourism and tourism management. The simplification and commercialisation of traditional recipes for tourism purposes is a form of cultural impoverishment, reducing community knowledge and practices to commercial stereotypes. This process contributes to the reproduction of a tourism system that is unsustainable - not only on an economic and structural level, but also on a cultural level. Thanks to their everyday familiarity with the production and management of waste, restaurateurs were conceptualised as strategic figures capable of conceptually redefining waste and transforming it into a cultural and material resource. They were also viewed as nodes for the complex connections within their communities and beyond. Their position in CLLs enabled the activation of new pathways of meaning - for example through the recovery of recipes in all their complexity, and through enhancing the value of local knowledge, thus renewing participatory cultural narratives. The use of drawings as part of the laboratories documented interactions and practices, but also critically reinterpreted the connections between restaurateurs, communities, and gastronomic memories, highlighting symbolic and emotional dimensions that are difficult to access through discursive analysis alone. This visual production acted as a catalyst for new perspectives and enriched the collective discussions by offering further insights into and understanding of the value of waste as a cultural and material resource.

Findings

The nature of tourism is paradoxical – it represents both a lifeline and a threat. On one hand, participants recognised tourism as a necessary driver of economic sustainability for their territories, seeing it as a means to combat depopulation. On the other hand, they also saw it as a force of erosion, endangering community cohesion, traditional knowledge, and local identities. This ambivalence situates tourism within broader contradictions, where systems of growth simultaneously sustain and exhaust the very resources—cultural, social, and ecological—on which they depend.

Across all narratives, cooking emerged as a recurring motif and was described by many participants as an “act of resistance.” Cooking became a performative and affective language through which memories and traditions are transmitted, re-embodied, and reclaimed. In this everyday practice, participants articulated the possibility of political and transformative

agency—a means to “bridge memories and territories” and to reassert the continuity of marginal and peripheral communities otherwise silenced by dominant tourism narratives. A case in point is the history of the *tìrcle* in the Belluno Dolomites. *Tìrcle*, traditional flour-and-egg fritters, were historically prepared for celebrations or community gatherings (es, Carnival, festa delle Donaze). Today, however, they have almost completely disappeared from the menus of restaurants and mountain huts, replaced by more easily marketable dishes such as French fries or polenta—the latter often mistakenly regarded as “authentically mountain” food, despite not being part of the region's original culinary tradition. This marginalisation of the *tìrcle* reflects the broader dynamics of homogenisation driven by tourism, in which local culinary identities are reduced to simplified and easily consumable representations. However, it is important to consider that the *tìrcle*, like any other aspect of traditional culture, cannot be understood as a static element, but rather as a porous cultural device capable of absorbing external influences while reworking and renewing elements within the community. The transformations it has undergone to respond to tourism should therefore not be interpreted solely as signs of loss, but also as forms of cultural adaptation and reworking, through which tradition is renewed and acquires new symbolic and social functions. *Tìrcle* are now being reimagined in a contemporary form. They are smaller, lightly fried, and now served not as a main course but as an appetiser or aperitif, accompanied by other small local delicacies. During a collaborative learning experience in the kitchen of a Ladin restaurant in Arabba, under the guidance of the artist, the research team analysed the preparation of *tìrcle* as a minor form of cultural resistance. For the occasion, they were made using natural food colourings that recalled the colours of the Ladin flag: green for the meadows, white for the snow, and blue for the sky. This experience showed that culinary practice functioned as a performative and affective device through which traditional recipes, gestures, and knowledge were revitalised and given new meaning. The act of cooking *tìrcle* emerged as a process of cultural re-signification, an ongoing dialogue between past and present, tradition and innovation. In this context, the material itself, comprising ingredients, shapes, and colours, became a vehicle for belonging and memory, as well as a space for symbolic negotiation, where tradition was reintroduced into new contexts of meaning. From this perspective, the reworking of *tìrcle* assumed the value of a symbolic and relational practice, capable of connecting memories and territories and reaffirming the historical and cultural continuity of marginal and peripheral communities, often silenced by dominant tourist narratives, while remaining in constant dialogue with the needs and transformations of the present.

Figure 1 Tircle Recipe

During the CLL in Venice, participants' speeches and drawings revealed cooking as both a practice of sustenance and also as a political act of memory and resistance, capable of opposing the processes of standardisation imposed by tourist economies and restoring dignity to everyday gestures of care and sharing. One of the recipes presented by participants was boiled meat, a dish widely enjoyed in the past and now experiencing a revival due to its ability to evoke a sense of home and bring people together around a warm meal. To prepare this dish, the chef selects cuts of meat that are now difficult to find but were once common, such as veal breast, veal tongue, or veal head. The chefs also experiment with the recipe, creating new types of sauces and ragù, and adding boiled beef.

In Venice, preparing the recipe and reworking the remaining leftovers also became a means of reactivating local knowledge, transforming this into tools for critical reflection and collective imagination. In this case, waste was treated as symbolic, establishing a parallel with the remnants of everyday life and industrialised hospitality, and highlighting the inherent tensions between consumption and renewal, exploitation and care. Through processes of artistic and participatory reworking, this waste became a tool for critique and a catalyst for imagining, allowing participants to envisage alternative futures grounded in situated and contextual knowledge, rather than the commodification of cultural heritage. In this case, working with waste also proved to be both a creative exercise and a political and cognitive act, capable of questioning dominant economic logic and restoring value to ordinary practices of care, transformation, and sharing.

Within the Creative Living Labs, the rediscovery of objects related to the preparation of tirle became a symbolic act of reappropriation: a way of reclaiming marginalised culinary practices and reaffirming a sense of belonging.

Below are some of the drawings the artist produced in response to interviews, observation, and the CCL. The drawings sum up the processes of experimentation, reflection, and revision that occurred during the activities.

INTERVISTE E LABORATORI

GLI ATTORI

Figure 2 The Methodology

CI SIAMO
INTERROGATI
SUL COSTO
ANCORA MOLTO
ALTO DELLE

BIOPLASTICHE

Figure 3 the methodology of inquiry

MOLTI RISTORATORI
HANNO IMMAGINATO
SOLUZIONI
PRAGMATICHE

.... E CONTINUA ...

Figure 4 The outcome of the living lab: pragmatic solution

Figure 5 The outcome of the living lab: image-led solution

Figure 6 The outcome of the living lab: reflections on the tourism and territory

Figure 7 The outcome of the living lab: reflections on marginalized communities, Ladin community

These reflections were then re-elaborated by the artist, following feedback of the research team, into an artist's book, published by Magonza Edition. The artist's took shape under the name ESAUSTE crystallises this collective process. The term, intentionally gendered and plural, expresses both a condition and a methodology. It reflects the exhaustion we encountered—in ourselves, when confronting academic logics, disciplinary fragmentation, and institutional expectations; and in the communities with whom we worked, strained by tourism models that consume rather than nourish, simplify rather than listen, extract rather than sustain. At the same time, "Esauste" alludes to a concrete starting point: ("Olio Esaustao" in Italian) used cooking oil. An everyday residue that, at first, we approached through a technical understanding of circularity—how to repurpose it, what materials it could generate, how its transformation might contribute to sustainable innovation. Yet, in this initial enthusiasm for a "virtuous transformation of waste," we recognised an underlying risk: replicating the same logic of economic accumulation that dominates tourism economies, where every residue must be converted into value without questioning the system that relentlessly produces waste, materially and symbolically. Our inquiry shifted from *how to recycle* to *what is discarded—and who is discarded*.

The artist book is based on origami, and can be read both as a small book and as a map, the book can be freely downloaded from the Publisher website (<https://magonzaeditore.it/it/product/esauste/>) or here:

The book collates and interprets the participants' inputs, visions, and suggestions, not as a neutral archive of possible re-uses for waste cooking oil, but as a curated assemblage of collective voices, a device of memory-work that resists erasure and commodification (Halbwachs, 2020). Indeed, the artist decided to deviate from the familiar process of creating new tools, objects, and souvenirs from waste, which would have risked perpetuating the same inherent practice of producing and creating waste. The artist's book works as an 'opening' device—a medium for dialogue that does not close off meaning, but rather multiplies channels for interpretation, prompting reflection on the paradox of the tourism monoculture in these territories.

The art-based research carried out was not limited to a communication or educational tool, but became a method of collective enquiry and resistance to prevailing models, perceived as far removed from local value systems.

Discussion

The final artworks show the contradictions inherent in prevailing narratives about sustainable tourism strategies, while challenging the techno-managerial optimism that underpins many models of the circular economy. Indeed, these artefacts did not aim to become consumable products, but rather functioned as performative mediators of shared meaning, enabling participants to recognise their experiences refracted through new cultural forms. Beyond their aesthetic value, the drawings served as tools for generating situated knowledge that challenges dominant narratives about waste. In this sense, they align with the perspective of waste as critique (Corvellec and Bevan, 2025), which interprets waste not simply as a material by-product but as a relational and political category that reveals exclusions, hierarchies, and asymmetries of power (Liboiron and Lepawsky, 2022; Gille, 2007). Embodying a form of waste-based critical epistemology, waste offered counter-narratives that challenged the linear logic of "take-make-waste" and opened new possibilities for thinking and acting differently in environments subject to overtourism.

The findings can be organised into three main categories, each reflecting different ways that culture and artistic production can be mobilised to engage with waste:

1. Refunctionalization/resourcification of waste. In this category, waste is intended as a resource to be transformed and recycled. In line with dominant circular economy narratives, waste was reimagined as a resource, converted into new commodities (promoted as green or sustainable), or a new form of energy production. Creativity as such is not mobilised in the process, or is only addressed in a marginal way to make said object aesthetically compelling. However, this risks reproducing extractive logic

and “wasting relations” (Liboiron and Lepawsky, 2022). This process does not challenge the idea of who (and which system) produces waste and who is then responsible for it, nor does it address or challenge the core issue of the tourism industry.

Figure 8: Refunctionalization/resourcification of waste

2. Reimagination of waste: Rather than generating new items for consumption, the process produced an imaginative tool that challenges the very notion of production. Creativity was mobilised to re-signify waste by transforming it into artefacts that mobilised memories and emotions. These may take the form of relational objects - for example, items created from waste cooking oil - that are not just materially “new” but are deeply embedded in personal and collective memory, dealing with issues relating to the carrying capacity of the city perceived as “under threat” from tourism. For example, these 'relational objects' created from waste cooking oil could be thermometers (for ‘measuring’ the maximum tourist capacity of the city), or creating new versions of objects used in the past to create traditional recipes such as tircle. While more generative and thoughtful, this approach still risks commodifying or stereotyping cultural practices and traditions.

Figure 8: Reimagination of waste

3. Caring for waste: The artistic process stimulated a profound reflection on the concept of waste that goes beyond the idea of material residue, interpreting it as a socially and politically constructed category which highlights practices of value attribution and processes of marginalisation. Care is understood here through an Haraway perspective. As Donna Haraway notes, “caring means becoming subject to the unsettling obligation of curiosity, which requires knowing more at the end of the day than at the beginning” (Haraway, 2008: 36). This approach contrasts with the optimistic narratives of waste as a resource, often presented as a positive rhetoric that extols humanity's heroic ability to solve even the most complex problems. Beyond the production of new objects, this approach privileged artefacts as non-products—performative mediators of ‘caring’ that escape market logic. Here, creativity foregrounded relationships and amplified voices which are otherwise marginalised in tourism

narratives, aligning with critical waste-based epistemologies (Corvellec and Bevan, 2025). Starting from waste cooking oil (WCO), a by-product of the tourism and hospitality industry, the artistic process pulled the threads of memory, affect, and embodied practice. Within the CLLs, WCO was not only treated as waste but also as a symbolic material that embodies the contradictions of overtourism: it is simultaneously a result of intensive consumption and a potential resource to activate creative processes that disrupt the linearity of the production–consumption–waste paradigm (Deleuze and Guattari, 1980; Armiero, 2021). Waste thus means stories, memories, and the vulnerability of the area and its people.

CARING FOR WASTE

Figure 9: Caring for waste

Thus, how do we care for waste besides artistic practice? Even though they were not asked direct questions about tourism, participants communicated via people, objects, memories, and emotions to share vivid memories of how the tourism industry has gradually transformed their everyday habits and their sense of place. They recalled, for instance, how traditional dishes such as *pastin* have almost disappeared from mountain huts, replaced by homogenised offers like French fries, and how the spread of large hotel chains has eroded local autonomy,

reshaping relationships between hosts and visitors into transactional ones. These reflections also revealed a growing awareness of the risks of tourism monocultures driven by large economic powers, which threaten to silence local voices and practices.

Amid these transformations, participants identified the kitchen as a generative space for new forms of local economy and sustainability.

Conclusions

In this research, artistic practices catalysed new forms of collective imagination. Starting from waste cooking oil, a by-product of the tourism and hospitality industry, the artistic process pulled the threads of memory, affect, and embodied practice. In the CLLs, used cooking oil was not only treated as waste but also as a symbolic entity that embodies the contradictions of overtourism – being simultaneously a (waste) product of intensive consumption and also a potential resource to activate creative processes that disrupt the linearity of the production–consumption–waste paradigm (Deleuze and Guattari, 1980; Armiero, 2021). The art-based approach revealed the contradictions inherent in prevailing narratives about sustainable tourism strategies, while challenging the techno-managerial optimism that underpins many models of the circular economy. Indeed, drawings enabled participants to recognise their experiences refracted through new cultural forms. By doing so, they resisted the commodification of culture and foregrounded alternatives for community, memory, and sustainability (Bartlett, 2015a; 2015b; Tarr, Gonzalez-Polledo, and Cornish, 2018). While thinking and making together, the participants implemented practices based on comparison, dialogue and creative thinking that are not usually applied in their sector - or at least not through creative experimentation based on drawing, memory and sharing personal experiences.

From these processes, several important lines of interpretation emerged:

- Critical reflection on the concept of waste, understood not only as material waste but also as a social and political category that reveals practices of attributing value and processes of marginalisation
- Highlighting the contradictions of sustainable tourism, which in some cases perpetuates unsustainable dynamics rather than transforming them
- Proposing alternative, bottom-up approaches capable of stimulating new perspectives for development within territories and tourism management - in particular how personal experience become collective when shared. Indeed the Living Lab experiments also embodied the affective and political dimension of caring for waste: by acknowledging exhaustion—of the communities—we created spaces where discarded elements could become mediators of dialogue, shared imagination, and situated knowledge.
- Imagining utopias: while utopian images may not appear to present practicable, realistic solutions to contemporary problems, they nonetheless present “a starting point for optimism” (Atkins et al., 2015: 651)

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